

Appendix of Empirical estimation of host galaxy dispersion measure towards well localized fast radio bursts

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1. Introduction

This is the Figure presented in the main paper.

Fig. 1. Upper: FRB20191001A host emission integrated at the narrow band (NB) encompassing H α using the same wavelength range as shown in the bottom panel. The blue circle is centered at the FRB localization and has a radius of $0.4''$ and the dashed black ellipse represents the actual FRB position uncertainty. Lower: The integrated spectrum of the H α emission within the blue circle (orange). We fit this emission with a Gaussian (dashed blue) plus a continuum (green).

2. H α emission for the rest of the sample

In Figures 2 to 12 we show, as in Figure 1 the location of the FRB within the host galaxy, along with the corresponding extracted spectrum for the rest of the sample, excluding FRB20191001A shown already in Figure 1. The galaxy map corresponds to the measured emission line (H α , H β , H γ , as appropriate).

Fig. 2. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20180924B.

Fig. 3. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20190102C.

Fig. 5. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20190611B. In this case, we cannot fit a Gaussian and thus just report a 2σ upper limit.

Fig. 4. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20190608B.

Fig. 6. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20190711A. In this case, instead of using H α we use H β and H γ .

Fig. 7. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20190714A.

Fig. 8. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20200430A.

Fig. 9. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20200906A.

Fig. 11. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20210320C.

Fig. 10. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20210117A. In this case, we cannot fit a Gaussian and thus just report a 2σ upper limit.

Fig. 12. Same as Figure 1 but for FRB20210410D.